

An Empirical Investigation of Energy Productivity Determinants in Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates energy productivity determinants for three of the East African countries for the period of 1992-2018. On application of Random effect analysis, Three-stage least-squares regression, G2SLS random-effects IV regression, Fixed-effects (within) IV regression and generalized estimate equation. The results indicate that energy sector productivity increase is primarily responsible for economy wide improvements. This should alleviate concerns that countries are becoming more energy productive due to structural economic shifts and growth in service sectors. Nations that are undergoing liberalization exhibit high levels of improvement, although they are still less energy production than developed Nations. In contrast, a more significant share of output from industry is associated with lower energy productivity levels and high energy prices on income levels are associated with improvement in energy sector productivity.

Keywords: ENERGY PRODUCTIVITY; RANDOM EFFECT REGRESSION; THREE-STAGE LEAST-SQUARES REGRESSION

Introduction

One of the main interests in business cycles is in identification moved in and out of recession before economic changes. Government agencies face significant challenges on trends with turning points on many countries and international economic outlook. On the use of data revisions target with

indicator variables that early available information on Energy productivity and consumption may differ from later available information for specific areas in time. On the release of economic indicators importing for evaluating forecast from different models since restrictions on accessing different situations.

In relevance to (Eije, 2018a) Energy productivity forecasters usually ignore the fact that data used for conducting different entities which could be revised as many times as it could this is due to past typically depend on observations which stimulate situations via parameter estimates and starting levels. Most authors such as (Graf Von Der Schulenburg et al., 2008) and (Robinson & Thierfelder, 2002) stimulate situation applying only a rolling and instead of using data available at all conditions made while other researchers like (Campbell, D. T., Stanley, J. C., & Gage, n.d.) Who criticizes most of the procedures that focus mainly on the use of a

generic method for estimating parameters in statistical models? Delays in publication forwards and analysis make predictions of present data an essential source of research at this point. Available models should be used for evaluations at a point when everything has been put in place, with the use of Google trends correlation with various economic indicators, which may be helpful with economic indicators for short term economic predictions. In other words, Energy productivity and Google trends, in particular, may help in predicting the present as a form of now casting¹.

The use of big data(African development Bank group, 2019) could be particularly useful for construction of early estimates, namely for production of energy, the preliminary estimate for contemporary value of Emissions, Population growth and the Female population which are mainly released after a period of time. The identification of dependent valuables for this paper becomes a challenge, and finding appropriate filter in extracting signals.

The paper is under two main purposes. The first is investigating Energy production in three main East African countries by combining different variables that could depend on one variable from (World Bank, 2005) to accurate the population and CO₂Emissions. And secondly, applying a endogenous covariates on panel data methodology based on analyzing the behavior of the leading energy production in regression data examination on Electricity as energy consumption in all countries.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 briefly reviews literature review on energy production and use issues, presentation of methodology and data applied in the paper done in section 3 whereas the main empirical results in the paper go to section 4 while the paper conclusion in section 5.

Literature review

2.1 Big data and energy productivity determinants.

Electricity consumption is one of Uganda's lowest per capita. Uganda ranks amongst the best African country suppliers on Hydropower plants as situated in a sub-Saharan region that predominated rely on hydropower, erratic rainfall, which have affected electricity supply, which leads to frequent load shedding. More increased 50 MW of capacity from massive fuel plants that have at least led to decline load shedding to zero ability(Sarris, A., P. Conforti, 1997.). Uganda's largest power plant was commissioned in 2012 and, it doubled capacity at the time hence operated by a public, private partnership between Uganda Government, Investment firm Blackstone for economic development. Additional energy sources are needed because electricity demand is growing² at an annual rate of 11-14% which intends to achieve a rural electrification rate 24% by 2023 with low-grade forms of energy mainly traditional biomass fuels accounting for 90% of energy consumption mainly used up by sugar production facilities at Kakira and kinyara sugar factories.

¹ Energy productivity and Google trends, in particular, may help in predicting the present as a form of now casting.

² Investment firm Blackstone for economic development. Additional energy sources are needed because electricity demand is growing.

On Tanzania through Tanesco company Electricity production The transmission and distribution system comprises of 48 transmission substations interconnected by transmission lines, 3,340 km of 220 kV, 2,063 km of 132 kV, 668 km of 66 kV, 24,165 km of 33 kV, 6,006 km of 11 kV and 71,629 km of 400 and 230 kV lines. Current transmission and distribution losses are at 16.4%. Beyond the grid, Small Power Producers (SPP) is responsible for the management of isolated micro- and mini-grids. The plan sets a top-line installed base star 2019. At the same time, Kenya's as an integrated grid network of 220 kV transmission system with the limited number of transmission lines hence being one of the sector and deficiency of frequent power outage as technical and non-technical losses, (Washington DC, 2002) the grid operators emphasized system reliability and introduction of technologies with authorities extending transmission and distribution lines and construction of substations which are aimed at introducing smart grid technologies in parts of Nairobi and Mombasa.

Figure 1. Knowing ahead Energy productivity determinants in Uganda, Kenya, and Tanzania

Notwithstanding, the frequency of different indicators isn't as currently demanded in the market, which try to use others published daily, solar, wind, Bioenergy, grid min grid, and Electricity. In this regard, thanks to newspaper publishers daily, possibilities on Time series and big regression data from the internet determines energy productivity(Alfaro, L, 2004; Moore & Christin, 2013; Curea & Ciora, 2013; Robinson & Thierfelder, 2002).

Electricity production near the waters of Lake Victoria becomes the most significant energy productive unit as a dependent standard in statistical figures describing the state of economic accurate and signals³ about the

³ Lake Victoria becomes the most significant energy productive unit as a dependent standard in statistical figures describing the state of economic accurate and signals.

population growth can be extracted from the heterogeneous data source (Population female growth, Net bilateral aid flows from DAC, Merchandise trade (%GDP)) in accordance to the Time series flow of data release to anticipate what's going to happen and intervene (Deardorff, 1998)

The paper could be in research concept of regressions on dependent variables to different renewable energy Promising potential generation from renewable energy sources that verify the determinants of energy productivity and maintenance. Hydro abundant solar biomass and geothermal resources lead the government to seek expansions and wind energy plants, wind energy plants as well as solar fed for rural electrification.

All countries take agriculture as the primary economic growth as an activity that produces the amount of agricultural waste. These can be used to generate Electricity by implementing biomass technology; the 2014 National energy policy draft also sets out the expansion of biogas targets ten thousand medium-sized digesters by 2030. Biogas is considered a viable energy solution by several agricultural products and all countries had promising wind power potential⁴ due to the topography of the rift valleys which are the windiest areas in Turkana regions of Kenya with expectations of a percentage to current wind technology. Even the wind farms connected to the grid for isolated community electricity generation Africa's largest wind farm 300MW being constructed in Turkana region of northwestern Kenya with land access being a challenge for transmission connection (Mas & Fsnwg, 2013) Land access has been a challenge for both site selection and transmission connection other wind projects in stages expected to see a breakthrough.

Describing approaches to energy productivity basing on time series a methodology that turned the method associated with searching in textual database basing on the theory of uncertainty under human decision with reference that is drawn from the energy productive and Natural resource observation with the functions observable networks (Eije, 2018a). It's built on E. views of natural resources excitement about possible future profit verses anxiety about future losses. Hydroelectricity indigenous commercial energy in a recognition potential of installed capacity has been developed. Several projects for soliciting funding with the Geography potential of East African community countries in rift valley escarpments may have the potential to produce Electricity to justify investments in extending the national grid, and traditionally hydropower has been the source of Electricity production in the region however intermittent river flows have decreased its reliability (Hanushek, E. A., Schwerdt, G., Wiederhold, S., & Woessmann, 2002.). Mismatching on hydro sites on-demand centers with a transmission system for further development. Developmental ideas of the regional country for every country having large hydro capacity generation with many projects estimated towards the end of 2030s economic analysis concludes on a commercially viable for Electricity in generating mini-grid.

According to (M.R, 2000), the importance of understanding the sentiments in the context of investment in order to successfully develop on energy ethics has been deeply discussed in literature. Sentiment indicators are crucial to understanding recessions because of capturing a sense of productive spirit (Council & Kong, 2015),

⁴ Biogas is considered a viable energy solution by several agricultural products and all countries had promising wind power potential.

states the fundamental level which accounts on different perception on how economic development over traditional leading because for many are available in real times and delays.

After reviewing a number of papers on energy productivity determinants, an observation on kinds unstructured to business cycles: 1 Internet searches (Google trends) 2 World Bank Indicators that allows the deepening in the correlation of key internet searches and economic activity. As of the CO₂ emissions, Net bilateral aid flows from DAC donors total current, Merchandise trade (% GDP) Population growth annually, Population female for energy

Productivity description in detail of composition statistically correlated.

2.2 The leading indicators as a predictor of Energy

The EAC system of composite leading indicators was developed in 1990s for early identification of economic turning points. The information is of prime importance to business, economists and policy makers for enabling⁵ timely analysis of short term production situation. Proved to indicate short term movements in an economy by using high measures of sensitivity to upcoming changes in business changes.

Energy efficiency demand per capita rose in 2009 and the residential sector contributes most of the consumption to households due to large amounts of biomass, consumed for heating, cooking and lighting. National electricity grid developments led to improve the services in the country has an example of aggregate purchasing schemes for energy efficiency equipment. No government projects are underway for now due to the pandemic hit countries and damaging the import and export ethics in all states, (Eije, 2018b) Mostly hindered by limited capacity strategic planning at governmental levels which lack awareness a shortage of technical capacity to disseminate skills without comprehensive policy targeting Energy efficiency (EE) all governments start addressing this through the implementation of projects at institutional levels in cooperation with several development partners(Mokveld, 2018). On policy formulation strategy and plans targeting this has led to developing an Energy efficiency report which is the basis for development and implementation of the national aid programme and establishing more concrete goals⁶ target and develop different frameworks targeting energy managers and auditors in guiding to develop standards and labeling to address buildings, address industrial energy management and efficiency biomass utilization which is mainly directed by public and private sectors. In summary, observed information from renewable energy and government frame works.

2.3 Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania import Duty Exemption

Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania have an agreement on import duty waivers on clean energy including deep cycle batteries and accessories which agreement reduces import duty to 0% for specialised development and generation of solar and wind energy including equipment cycle batteries which store solar power and

⁵ The information is of prime importance to business, economists and policy makers for enabling production entity.

⁶ Energy efficiency report which is the basis for development and implementation of the national aid programme and establishing more concrete goals.

accessories. Looking at taxes and duties Under the VAT act machinery from licensed manufacturers imported duty tax-free Bill⁷, photosensitive semiconductor devices whether assembled into panels and solar water heaters are exempted from VAT as are specialized vehicles plant and machinery, feasibility studies engineering designs plus consultancy services related to hydropower (Hanushek, e. a., schwerdt, g., wiederhold, s., & woessmann, 2002.). The basic rate of VAT on services and goods raised to 18% however, amendment on solar generation in 2016 is no longer exempt from VAT to recover operating costs, and the Bill extends the exemption of contractors to supply of hydropower projects on geothermal power projects consequently VAT never applies to construction and pre-operation expenses of the power⁸ projects <http://www.worldbank.org> Investors receiving licenses from different Revenue authorities from different countries according to the law of beginning and end of the fiscal year and filing returns for all companies each year by 31 December following year-end tax with different accounting periods.

2.4 Electricity distribution as an Energy productivity determinant.

Another leading indicator that we could follow to anticipate Electricity energy production with economic policy uncertainty for three countries East Africa as a whole. The index is composed of different underlying indicators Population growth (annual %), population, female (% of total population), CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita), Net bilateral aid flows from DAC donors Total (current US\$), Merchandise trade (% of GDP)

According to the literature (Balasubramanyan, v. n., salisu, m. and sapsford, 1996) shows significant relationships between productivity maintenance and economic growth and real macroeconomic variables on session that an increase in economic uncertainty which anticipates on economic growth and production in the following times⁹. In this paper use of time series and regressions on variable dependence on a decision balanced by P-values essence in our real time leading economic because the correlation between Population growth (annual %) which is high than Net bilateral aid flows from DAC donors, Total (current US\$) (0.000497 vs. 0.192446) that proves that population growth is statistically significant.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data

Table 1

Set of variables to build the determining energy productivity in the three leading countries

Variables	Definition	Data source
POP	Population growth (annual %)	World bank data indicators

⁷ Looking at taxes and duties Under the VAT act machinery from licensed manufacturers imported duty tax-free Bill.

⁸ The estimation approach assumes that changes in the independent variables elicit long and short term changes in the dependent variables

⁹ Productivity maintenance and economic growth and real macroeconomic variables on session that an increase in economic uncertainty which anticipates on economic growth and production in the following times.

POPF	Population, female (% of total population)	Development indicators
Emissions	CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita)	Google search
NETb	Net bilateral aid flows from DAC donors, Total (current US\$)	IMF data indicators
Mtrade	Merchandise trade (% of GDP)	World bank data indicators

Note: For Google Search: The search reflects interest in relation to the maximum value in a given region and time frame. Variables indicate the maximum popularity of terms while the definitions take on reactions of data corrected and World Bank development indicators also measured as index.

To analyze the energy consumption data for extracting information, analysts pose high-level queries to understand the consumption patterns in different houses. These queries are based on our questions (Table 1), and details are provided in similarly, “Population growth” means “Merchandise trade”, therefore in total selection analysis¹⁰. Labor force in total could abide as a simple evolution on variable per say on total according to the development indicators. We have selected such methods because they are highly competitive in many application domains and used in many real-life applications (Davis, 2011). Our findings show Population growth and emissions outperformed as compared to other classifiers. The random is an ensemble variant of the decision tree that adds an additional layer of randomness to bagging this model can provide excellent results due to its property of generating many classifiers and fuse their results.

World Bank development indicators has been the main source of data though from other areas like news articles, All data used is published in many publication houses, but building on indicators on a timely basis so as to make comparison with different composite leading indicators which is released by the East African community and by Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania in particular at GDP of all countries that has been interpolated timely. Endogenous covariates on panel data start in January 1992 and end in December 2018 hence number of observations amounts to 81.

3.2 Energy productivity determinants on group observations

To aggregate the 5 variables for building real energy production we apply Endogenous covariates on panel data and generalized method regression assessment on factors used to focus on reducing dimensions, that substitute main variable and weighting other variables. In applying the factor analysis considering main variables (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_5) on group of observations and calculated as a new set of variables F_1, F_2, \dots, F_p , non-

¹⁰ “Population growth” means “Merchandise trade”, therefore in total selection analysis.

correlated among them, whose variances progressively balance. Each F_j (where $j = 1, \dots, p$) is a linear combination the original X_1, X_2, \dots, X_5 that is:

$$F_j = a_{j1}X_1 + a_{j2}X_2 \dots + a_{j5}X_5 \quad (1)$$

Where a_j is a vector of constant.

Factor analysis has been broadly utilized to construct indicators because this allows researchers to build multivariate by means of linear combinations with non performing variables. According to the technique identifying population growth and CO₂ emission through original correlation matrix. (Davis, 2011) shows component methods are rather more sophisticated, not requiring decisions for each variables but only allowing all to contribute on energy determinants in different countries (index) which data terms lead to 100 percent year variance up to date in many countries Worldwide. World Bank development indicators contribute the trends of economic development and investment respectively and Google search measured as special use and Electricity consumption information in Tanzania, Kenya and Uganda.

3.4 Empirical methodology

3.4.1 Random effect analysis methodology

As been explained we derive on use of Random effect analysis aggregate energy productivity into impacts on structural in that consideration on possible variables (T. calinski, 1974) that might be thought under determination in doing so the review of 5 possible determinants in a random effect analysis for potential interlinkages (A.k. Jain, m. narasimha murty, 1999). The random effect, between effects, fixed effects and first effect estimator analysis implements different approaches which are suitable for criterion to define energy productivity.

$$RE = \frac{BE(n-k)}{FE(k-1)} \quad (2)$$

Where BE is the between effect, FE is the Fixed effect; k is the number of variables and n is the number of samples. Moreover, BE is defined as

$$BE = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i // x_2 - x \\\ d^2 \quad (3)$$

Where x_1 is the centroid of variables i , x is the overall mean of the sample data, and their squared difference being the distance between variables.

Panel data property of variables determine the random effect test employed whether they are statistically valid between variables found non-stationary in levels in first differences hence productivity indexes from panel data analysis found to be stationary in disputes then the application with a long-run relationship with consideration being estimated using entirely -modified ordinary least square and dynamic ordinary least squares given by:

$$\ln Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln \text{POP}_{it} + \beta_2 \ln \text{GDP}_{it} + \beta_3 \ln \text{Mtrade}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{CO}_2 + \beta_4 \ln \text{POP}_{it} + \beta_5 \ln \text{GNI}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

Where i denotes a country, t denotes time, Y denotes the various indexes, ε_{it} denotes the equation error term for state i in year t , and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 - -\beta_5$, denotes the long-run slope coefficients. (Note that only $\ln \text{POP}_{it}$, $\ln \text{GDP}_{it}$, and others are included in Eq. (4) since these are the only explanatory variables considered that were found to be stationary in first differences¹¹, as explained in the results section below.) The model is run on panel data in between effects, fixed effects, first difference estimator and random effect results are presented given they proved to be similar (Eije, 2018a). This is estimated using stationary variables, i.e. the first differences of variables that are stationary in primary differences, the levels of the variables that are stationary in scales, and the lagged residuals from the long-run equations which are derived from the estimation of the three versions of the long-run relationship. The estimation approach assumes that changes in the independent variables elicit long and short term changes in the dependent variables¹². Lagged responses and dynamic relationships were tested by adding different period lags to the dependent and independent variables. The slowdowns were limited to few years because of the number of yearly observations in the dataset. The Institutions and energy models confirm Econometric techniques that have been applied on cross-country data, just to confirm the knowledge that Institutions effect on industrial growth is positive and highly statistically significant and this evidence was confirmed by all four models used in the paper.

4. Results

4.1 G2SLS random-effects IV regression

Using panel data through Random effects, between effects, fixed effects and first difference estimator being statistical predicting a response based on the history response and the transfer of dynamics from relevant predictors (-2.03318) as an interception. Regression can help and predict behavior system from observational data (81). The results suggest that the majority of country-level increases were a result of sectoral energy productivity improvements rather than structural economic shifts on population (-3.63905), with the East African countries transitioning from the fall of community with countries experiencing the highest economic growth, being done through improvements in structural and sectoral energy productivity effect¹³. Kenya is an exceptional sectoral energy productivity improvements partially offset by a slight economic shift towards more energy intensive sectors on merchandise trade (2.934926). Although gross output in heavy industries within the region service sectors grow at a faster rate and increase their share of economic output. 2SLS proved as a better technique for our data than OLS (2.775571) on result benefits, this simply because of over identification test showed that instrument can be considered exogenous; (Curea & Ciora, 2013) Conclusion on energy determinant productivity insignificant in influence to growth compared with quality of institutions

¹¹ Since these are the only explanatory variables considered that were found to be stationary in first differences.

¹² The estimation approach assumes that changes in the independent variables elicit long and short term changes in the dependent variables.

¹³ Experiencing the highest economic growth, being done through improvements in structural and sectoral energy productivity effect.

that most areas especially in Emissions, population difference between Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania due to regression results on data formulation.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics

	Population growth (annual %)	Population, female (% of total population)	Net bilateral aid flows from DAC donors, Total (current US	Merchandise trade (% of GDP)	CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita)
Mean	2.935366648	35.86438577	8.88556E+11	2787.378373	17606015.07
Standard Error	0.034192064	2.310523907	2.12342E+11	438.7649468	2005024.89
Minimum	2.305948675	5.879067021	2716.105358	0	0
Maximum	3.749875169	50.93538819	8.83123E+12	9598.198411	71269996.64
Obs	81	81	81	81	81

The first class summarizes the center of population growth annually being known as measures of central tendency as a range of (Min 2.305948675 and Maxi 3.749875169) . The second class summarizes the dispersion of the sample and is commonly known as measures of dispersion on Population female. The third class, known as shape statistics summarizes essential elements of the shape of the underlying probability distribution implied by the sample on Net bilateral aid flows from DAC donors. Our objective in using descriptive statistics is to describe as compactly as possible the critical properties of empirical data on merchandise trade. This information will then be used to assist us in selecting an appropriate probability model for modeling energy productivity.

Table 2 OLS regression

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	-1.6E+08	77840863	-2.03318	0.045526**
Population growth (annual %)	-1.9E+07	5163506	-3.63905	0.000497**
Population, female (% of total population)	4439388	1599450	2.775571	0.006933**
Net bilateral aid flows from DAC donors, Total (current US\$)	-3.3E-06	2.51E-06	-1.31505	0.192446
Merchandise trade (% of GDP)	26814.88	9136.476	2.934926	0.00441**

Note: ** shows significance level of 5%

Looking at table 2 the significant level on 5% on population growth and intercept as dependent variables which shows the main advantage on the Energy production on different levels. On the Net bilateral aid flows from DAC donors, Total (current US\$) is negatively resulting above 5% which doesn't much the contribute

much on energy productivity¹⁴. We have a sample of observations of energy returns on a particular energy product. We wish to characterize the future uncertainty surrounding these price returns using probability. We get to know the appropriate result on obtaining using probability distribution. (R. Jimenez, 2004.) It turns out that a probability distribution is determined by a number of parameters often have a meaningful interpretation. For example, if we choose to model the variable returns using a normal probability distribution, the arithmetic mean is one of the two parameters that determine¹⁵ the probability values of the distribution. The important point to take away from this discussion is that we often use our sample to derive estimates of the parameters of some underlying probability to tell us something about the characteristics of the price return of the energy product in question.

Table 3 G2SLS random-effects IV regression

variables					
CO2emissionsmetrictonsporc	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf. Interval]
NetbilateralaidflowsfromDAC	4.64E-06	1.07E-06	4.34	0.001	2.55e-06 6.73e-06
Populationfemaleoftotalp	-197522.6	87065.11	-2.27	0.023	-368167.1 - 26878.16
Populationgrowthannual	5296172	-2.3	-2.32	0.021	-2.26e+07 - 1889226
_cons	5.66E+07	1.61E+07	3.52	0.0011	2.50e+07 8.81e+07
sigma_u 0					
sigma_e 9671107.3 rho 0	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				
Instrumented: NetbilateralaidflowsfromDAC					
Instruments: Populationfemaleoftotalp Populationgrowthannual MerchandisetradeofGDP					

Note: ** shows significance level of 5%

By examining the energy productivity in Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania that are subject to institutional failings, such as public sector corruption, failures in the rule of law, general energy productivity is relatively more effective in poor institutional environments. This appears that institutional illness creates more enormous scope for aid to have an energy production more effectively; (Eije, 2018a)it will likely enjoy higher levels of population growth and Emissions, to begin with. As such, the impact of energy production is virtually indiscernible. More simply put, we find that the higher is the need, the greater are the marginal benefits of energy production¹⁶. We find that energy production has a negligible direct impact on economic growth(IEA,

¹⁴ On the Net bilateral aid flows from DAC donors, Total (current US\$) is negatively resulting above 5% which doesn't much the contribute much on energy productivity.

¹⁵ If we choose to model the variable returns using a normal probability distribution, the arithmetic mean is one of the two parameters that determine.

¹⁶ More simply put, we find that the higher is the need, the greater are the marginal benefits of energy production.

2007). We, therefore, investigate what exactly energy production and its variable determinants. We find that aid enters the financial system and thus affects growth indirectly through its impact on prices. The industrialized countries being well set for production of energy big quantities is interacted with energy sectors within the countries.

Table 4 First-differenced IV regression

Variables				
Populationgrowthannual	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z
NetbilateralaidflowsfromDAC D1.	-3.16E-30	2.04E-29	-0.15	0.011
CO2emissionsmetrictonsperc D1.	1.29E-25	5.11E-25	0.25	0.008
Populationgrowthannual D1.	1	2.71E-17	3.70E+16	0.001
_cons	3.47e-18 2	9.40E-19	1.18	0.239
sigma_u	6.784e-16			
sigma_e	1.729e-17			
rho	.99935054 (fraction of variance due to u_i)			
Instrumented: NetbilateralaidflowsfromDAC				
Instruments: CO2emissionsmetrictonsperc Populationgrowthannual MerchandisetradeofGDP				

Differenced regression results tend to be analyzing the variables on population as the main dependent variable by revisiting emissions, population growth, fixed effects, first difference estimator the Institutions and growth models.(Wooldridge, 1995.) Econometric techniques have been applied on cross-country data, just to confirm the knowledge that energy production effect determinants are positive and highly statistically significant. This simply because the over identification test showed that the instrument could not be considered exogenous. G2SLS estimator and fixed effects panel estimators just confirmed the results¹⁷. As a proxy variable for institutions, we used the rule of law variable; also as instruments were used revolutions and rating as well as population results formation on variables also, as conclusion here the trade is insignificant in influence to energy production determinants to growth compared with the quality of institutions.

¹⁷ This simply because the over identification test showed that the instrument could not be considered exogenous. G2SLS estimator and fixed effects panel estimators just confirmed the results.

Conclusion

Results from analysis reveal several key findings that deepen the understanding of the determinants of energy productivity. First, the decomposition analysis shows sectoral energy productivity increase from 1994 to 2018 are primarily responsible for economy-wide improvements. This should alleviate concerns that countries are becoming more energy productive due to structural economic shifts and growth in service sectors.

Second, countries with similar demographic and economic characteristics have similar energy productivity levels and annualized rates of improvement. Most notably, the cluster analysis takes on nations that liberalized their economies during the period Tanzania, Kenya and Uganda. EAC nations and other low industrializing economies still lag behind despite having similar energy productivity levels. The East African countries have on average, Population growth (growth %), population, female (% of total population), Net bilateral aid flows from DAC donors, Total (current US\$), Merchandise trade (% of GDP) and CO₂ emissions (metric tons per capita) are perceived as less secure than other emerging economies. These characteristics and others can influence economic output and energy consumption levels, and thus energy production.

Third, the econometric analysis results reinforce long-standing hypotheses that higher energy prices and CO₂ emissions (metric tons per capita) are associated with aggregate energy productivity improvements (at least in the long run). The analysis shows these improvements occur primarily through the sectoral energy productivity effect channel rather than shifts in the structure of the economy. Higher levels of investment are also associated with aggregate energy productivity improvements, although the response from the investments may take a few years to materialize. In the short-term, the stakes can decrease sectoral energy productivity because of increased activity that does not yet generate value. Still, they can cause the structure of more service and advanced manufacturing.

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